

A Lightweight DCGAN Approach for Synthetic Pulmonary Image Generation and Data Augmentation

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Abstract:

In spite of major advances in thoracic imaging, chest radiography remains a primary diagnostic reference tool, yet the development of reliable deep learning models for automated detection is often severely limited by the shortage of medical datasets. Annotated lung imaging datasets are particularly scarce, either due to heterogeneity in acquisition protocols across institutions or to the lack of expert annotations, which critically limits the deployment of robust pneumonia detection models. In this context, synthetic data generation emerges as a promising avenue for enriching training datasets, provided that generative models are adapted and configured to produce realistic and clinically relevant images that faithfully reflect the anatomical and pathological features observed in real lung imaging.

To address this data gap, this work proposes the use of data generation techniques, specifically a deep convolutional generative adversarial network (DCGAN), to generate realistic synthetic radiographic images, thereby enriching training datasets for improved pneumonia detection. The architecture combines a generator with transposed convolutional layers (BatchNorm + ReLU) for progressive image synthesis from a latent vector, and a discriminator with variable-step convolutional layers (LeakyReLU + Sigmoid), jointly trained via an adversarial minimax loss function. Two experiments were conducted on the Kaggle Chest X-Ray dataset: Experiment 1 on a CPU (128 × 128 px, 20 epochs, batch size 2) and Experiment 2 on a Tesla T4 GPU (256 × 256 px, 50 epochs, batch size 32). The latter incorporated spectral normalization of the discriminator and a StepLR scheduler for improved training stability. Experiment 1 diverged after the 10th epoch, with increasing generator loss (from 1.41 to 1.91) and a FID of 515.20 in 9.26 hours. Experiment 2 achieved stable convergence, with generator loss decreasing from 2.68 to 1.61, a FID of 503.19, and a training time of only 0.93 hours, with optimal image quality at epoch 35. A refined ResNet-18 classifier on the augmented dataset confirmed a recall of 1.0000 (+0.64%), thus reducing false negatives, a critical factor for pneumonia screening. These results confirm that GPU-accelerated DCGAN, combined higher resolution and stabilization techniques, offers an effective solution to the data shortage problem in pulmonary medical imaging.

Keywords : DCGAN; Chest X-Ray; Pneumonia; Data Augmentation; Spectral Normalization; Medical Image Synthesis